

THE ROLE OF INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS

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Annotation

This article is about the application of technology as audiolingualism, and when it first became popular, tape recorders and audiovisual equipment often played a large role in audiolingualism, providing accurate models of dialogues and exercises.

Аннотация

Эта статья дано о применени технологии как аудиолингвизм, и когда она впервые стала популярной, магнитофоны и аудиовизуальное оборудование часто играли большую роль в аудиолингвизме, обеспечивая точные модели диалогов и упражнений.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola texnologiyani audiolingualizm sifatida qo'llash haqida bo'lib, u birinchi marta mashhur bo'lganida, magnitofonlar va audiovizual uskunalalar ko'pincha dialoglar va mashqlarning aniq modellarini taqdim etadigan audiolingualizmda katta rol o'ynagan.

International materials is the Audiolingual method assist the teacher to develop languages mastery in the learner. They are primarily teacher oriented. A student textbook is often need used in the elementary phases of a course where students are primarily listening, repeating, and responding. At this stage in learning, exposure to the printed word may not be considered teacher's book that contains the structured sequence of lessons to be followed and the dialog able, because it diverts attention from the aural input. The teacher, however, will have access drills, and other practice activities. When textbooks and printed materials are introduced to the student, they provide the texts of dialogues and cues needed for drills and exercises.

Technology had an important role to play in Audiolingualism, and when it first became popular tape recorders and audiovisual equipment often had central roles in an audiolingu vided accurate models for dialogues and drills. The language laboratory was also an inno course. If the teacher was not a native speaker of the target language, the tape recorder pr work and to receive controlled error-free practice of basic structures. It also adds variety by tion that was essential in an audiolingual course. It provides the opportunity for further d providing an alternative to classroom practice. A recorded lesson in the audio programma first present a dialogue for listening practice, allow for the student to repeat the sentenc the dialogue line by line, and provide follow-up fluency drills on grammar or pronunciation.

Procedure

Since Audiolingualism is primarily an oral approach to language teaching, it is not surprising that the process of teaching involves extensive oral instruction. The focus of instruction is on immediate and accurate speech; there is little provision for grammatical explanation or talking about the language. As far as possible, the target language is used as the medium of instruction and translation or use of the native language is discouraged. Classes of ten or fewer are considered optimal, although larger classes are often the norm. Brooks (1964: 142) lists the following procedures that the teacher should adopt in using the Audiolingual **Method**:

- The modeling of all learnings by the teacher.

- The subordination of the mother tongue to the second language by rendering English inactive while the new language is being learned.
- symbols.
- The early and continued training of the ear and tongue without recourse to graphic.
- The learning of structure through the practice of patterns of sound, order, and form rather than by explanation.
- The gradual substitution of graphic symbols for sounds after sounds as thoroughly known.
- The summarizing of the main principles of structure for the student's when the structures are already familiar, especially when they differ from those of the mother tongue...
- The shortening of the time span between a performance and the pronouncement of its rightness or wrongness, without interrupting the response. This enhances the factor of reinforcement in learning.
- The minimizing of vocabulary until all common structures have been learned. . The study of vocabulary only in context..
- Sustained practice in the use of the language only in the molecular form of speaker hearer-situation.
- Practice in translation only as a literary exercise at an advanced level.

In a typical audiolingual lesson, the following procedures would be observed:

1. Students first hear a model dialogue (either read by the teacher or on tape) containing the key structures that are the focus of the lesson. They repeat each line of the dialogue. individually and in chorus. The teacher pays attention to pronunciation, intonation, and fluency. Correction of mistakes of pronunciation or grammar is direct and immediate. The dialogue is memorized gradually, line by line. A line may be broken down into several phrases if necessary. The dialogue is read aloud in chorus, one half saying one speaker's part and the other half responding. The students do not consult their book throughout this phase.
2. The dialogue is adapted to the students' interest or situation, through changing certain key words or phrases. This is acted out by the students.
3. Certain key structures from the dialogue are selected and used as the basis for pattern drills of different kinds. These are first practiced in chorus and then individually. Some grammatical explanation may be offered at this point, but this is kept to an absolute minimum.
4. The students may refer to their textbook, and follow-up reading, writing, or vocabulary activities based on the dialogue may be introduced. At the beginning level, writing is purely imitative and consists of little more than copying out sentences that have been practiced. As proficiency increases, students may write out variations of structural items they have practiced or write short compositions on given topics with the help of framing questions, which will guide their use of the language.
5. Follow-up activities may take place in the language laboratory, where further dialogue and drill work is carried out.

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